

Hybrid Provision of Energy based on Reliability and Resiliency by Integration of Dc Equipment

Work Package WP5

Open and secure ICT for modular resilient optimized hybrid grid

Deliverable D5.2

FIWARE IoT Agent based Sensing and Monitoring infrastructure layer

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Co-author(s):	Kazmi Jawad (AIT); Francesco Bellesini (EMOT)
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List of Abbreviations

AC	Alternating Current
ACDC	Alternating Current and Direct Current
API	Application Programming Interface
BEMS	Building Energy Management Systems
CIM	Common Information Model
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DC	Direct Current
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
GE	Generical Enabler
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IED	Intelligent Electronic Device
IoT	Internet of Things
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
MQTT	Message Queue Telemetry Transport
NGSI-LD	Next Generation Service Interface Linked Data
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PID	Proportional-Integral-Derivative
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
PMUs	Phasor Measurement Units
REST	Representational State Transfer
SAREF	Smart Appliances REference
SARGON	SmArt eneRGy dOmain oNtology
SG	Smart Grid
SQL	Structured Query Language

Executive Summary

The HYPERRIDE sensing and infrastructure layer is described in this document. This layer provides an interface for the data collection and transmission from Hybrid Alternating Current and Direct Current (ACDC) networks. The data collected by the field instruments will be provided to the Information and Communications Technology (ICT) platform according to the current data model. The currently applied ontology is SmArt eneRGy dOmain oNtology (SARGON) ontology, which is an extension of Smart Appliances REference (SAREF) ontology for power systems and building automation applications. The developed layer extends the existing DC and AC monitoring infrastructures (e.g. FISMEP platform) by adopting and upscaling FIWARE IoT Agent and Context Broker. The sensing and monitoring layer is based on the open source software tools: Grafana, Message Queue Telemetry Transport (MQTT) Broker, Keycloak, Internet of Things (IoT) Agent, MongoDB, Entirety, Create DB, QuantumLeap and Orion Context Broker. The use of Entirety overcomes the challenges of the mapping between the different network protocols and generation of JSON-LD based on Web Ontology Language (OWL) files. Therefore, the sensing process will be simple and unified. The monitoring is based on the open-source tool Grafana, which leverages the best open-source observability software. In order to prove the concept, the developed platform has been tested in the German Pilot real-time device simulator. The switch gear data is collected through MQTT broker, harmonized according to the ontology, and monitored in the Grafana dashboard. This shows the success of the process of data sensing and monitoring. The software tool is publicly available in the following repository: <https://github.com/zhiyupan/HYPERRIDE-sensing-and-monitoring-layer>.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

The goal of this document is to provide a description of HYPERRIDE sensing and infrastructure layer. This layer is a tailored interface for the data collection from Hybrid ACDC networks and the transmission of commands/setpoints for the safe and reliable operation of the system. The data collected by the field instruments will be provided to the developed ICT platform according to the developed data model. The sensing and monitoring layer specification is technology-independent and provides a reference implementation. The developed platform extends the existing Direct Current (DC) and Alternating Current (AC) monitoring infrastructures by adopting and upscaling FIWARE IoT Agent and Context Broker. This document also provide a example of how to use the developed platform to monitor the device.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 1 provides information about the report content whereas Section 2 introduces the HYPERRIDE sensing and monitoring infrastructure layer. Section 3 describes the experiment in the German pilot. The deliverable is concluded in Section 4.

2 HYPERRIDE Sensing and Monitoring infrastructure Layer

In this section, the HYPERRIDE sensing and monitoring infrastructure layer is described in detail. First, a description of the ACDC Grid Monitoring Device is given.

2.1 ACDC Grid Monitoring Device

In HYPERRIDE several IoT devices are involved for real-time monitoring and remote management, enabling smart energy management of distributed renewable energy plants, charging stations, storage systems and loads. Regarding hybrid ACDC grid monitoring, two different channels are typically used for data collection from smart meters deployed; the first channel is Power Line Communication (PLC) in the 9 kHz - 95 kHz frequency range (CEI - EN 50065-1) whilst the second channel is GSM/GPRS. In ACDC hybrid grid, new generation smart meters

Figure 1: Monitoring devices in Italian hybrid ACDC grid.

with more frequent sampling have been deployed to support real-time operations, providing data in JSON format every 5 seconds; namely, smart meter extension (SMX) connected to digital meter and power quality analyzer. Furthermore, in some of the critical points of hybrid ACDC grid have also been deployed phasor measurement units (PMUs). Measurements from PMUs are precisely time-stamped, using a common time synchronization source such as global positioning system (GPS), and include information about AC grid's frequency, rate of change of frequency (RoCoF) as well as angle and magnitude measurements of both voltages and currents, commonly referred to as synchrophasors. Connectivity to the devices is provided through dedicated 4G routers and APN for local connection; at the same time, communication with other companies is provided by means of a VPN channel. Data generated by PMU is saved as JSON objects and transmitted to the central broker every second. Moreover, for a secure and encrypted communication, a based cryptographic technology, called Physical Unclonable Function (PUF) has been integrated in the PMU device to offer a decentralized trust & identity management mechanism, supporting end-users privacy by design. An additional monitoring IoT device is related to charging station deployed in hybrid ACDC grid; it exchange data through a modem connected to a single-board computer, generally a Raspberry Pi; charg-

ing station protocols are OCPP, an application protocol for communication between charging stations and EMOT central management system, and websocket, a computer communications protocol, providing full-duplex communication channels over a single TCP connection. OCPP

Figure 2: Raspberry Pi 3 installed in EMOT charging station.

server accepts communications and data exchange only with the client program that is installed in the charging station computer. The client has an authentication key that is assigned to it by the charging station management software when creating a new charging station. Charging station data format is JSON and the sampling rate is one second.

2.2 ACDC Grid Data Model

IoT and Edge-base technologies are being investigated for numerous applications in Smart Grid (SG) especially monitoring and control. There are however certain challenges due to the fragmentation of standards, platforms, services, and technologies. Additionally, there is a challenge to address the heterogeneity in information and data representation coming from or going into the, possibly millions of, IoT devices coordinating together. One possible solution to overcoming this heterogeneity challenge is with a semantic layer that can deal with the sheer size and complexity of this data in an interoperable manner.

The SAREF ontology (see D5.4 (Kazmi et al., 2021)) was created in 2015 to connect data from smart devices and make it easier for IoT devices that adhere to various protocols and standards to communicate with one another.

As a basis for the SARGON, a set of use cases and existing data models have been identified and they can be summarised as follows (Haghighi et al., 2020):

1. Automation of medium voltage distribution grids: it considers the inclusion of DC technology for which the grid is operated as a hybrid ACDC power grid. For this use case,

- the Intelligent Electronic Device (IED) is used to monitor the grid. Currently, the standard IEC-61850 constitutes a well-received reference for the automation of distribution grids. The extension proposed in SARGON consists of reformulating the data structure used in IEC-61850 according to an ontology description, as well as introducing devices specifically related to hybrid ACDC grids, such as power converters or DC switches;
2. PMU interaction and data visualization: Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs) find more and more applications in the monitoring and control of the electrical grid, not only in the transmission networks but also in the distribution ones. The PMUs interaction with the connected devices, as well as the data-driven applications that exploit the obtained measurements, constitute a worthwhile field for the SAREF expansion. Therefore, PMU as a type of metering device is included in the SARGON ontology;
 3. Building automation and monitoring: The control of energy demand in buildings such as gas, electricity, hot water, etc., and its optimization. It involves the deployment of Building Energy Management Systems (BEMS), which relies on the interaction with smart meters and actuator devices to effectively operate each functionality. Moreover, the user involvement in the overall process is an undeniable constituent, which has to be included in the ontology representation of the building automation domain;
 4. Energy management with residential/non-residential involvement: In order to optimize the overall energy management with residential/non-residential involvement, the utilities have to expand the energy control. Therefore, the SARGON must include the entire city district, as a building agglomeration. Control algorithms are implemented on local hardware Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) and the connection between the PLC, sensors, and actuators are frequently realized by either wired analog signals (0–10 V) or by wired bus systems. SARGON has been considered for the modern building energy systems, especially in residential/non-residential buildings, which includes plenty of sensors and actuators in order to achieve a proper operation besides the building operation task;
 5. Energy management at the building/district level: It targets the interaction between the energy management of buildings/districts and their electrical automation. Hence, it considers the control functionalities and the data/measurements that combine these aspects. For instance, SARGON includes use cases to control the installed electrical devices in the building. For this reason, it has a building information domain connected to the list of devices defined for building automation and electrical system monitoring.

Figure 3 gives a picture of the complexity of the SARGON ontology, which aggregates cross-cut domain-specific information. Modularity is one of the main advantages of the SARGON ontology; this allows further development of new elements necessary to fill possible gaps and supports any additional development of missing information models.

The SARGON ontology network consists of several interconnected domain ontologies related to the SG and building automation:

- Person, Company, Building, and Address ontologies contain data for describing the nature of a person, company, building, and address, besides spaces and geometrical data such as area, place, floors, etc.;
- Device inherits all classes of SAREF ontology and extends it according to energy equipment which includes industrial equipment, energy generators, and system resources, such as PMUs, Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controllers, converters, etc.;
- Services provides ontologies for services in the SG and building automation like control-

Figure 3: Overview of the SARGON ontology (Haghighi et al., 2020).

ling, monitoring and protection;

- Common Information Model (CIM) and International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) 61850 present terms and relations in the power grids. It identifies the list of classes and variant instances that can be used for monitoring and controlling of SGs according to the standards.

The ontology of the SARGON network has been harmonized to enable data portability for different applications in smart energy systems including, but not limited, to building automation and power grid controlling/monitoring. They are intended to be used together with FIWARE Next Generation Service Interface Linked Data (NGSI-LD), a standard defined by European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) Industry Specification Group for cross-cutting Context Information Management (GS, 2020). The ontology covers Building and Device domains and connects these two domains according to the concept of Linked-Data. Figure 4 represents the graph visualization of the ontology with a view of classes in Web Protégé ¹.

2.3 Platform Overview

There are various sources of data from historical facts to human surveys. These data have very less use if it is not processed or if it is not analyzed. There could be different ways to analyze the data, and one of them could be by graphical visualization. Now, getting the data from the source to the visual representation may include countless steps depending on the type of project. Some common steps are getting the data, inputting the data (manually or automatically), processing the data, uploading the data into a database, and finally displaying the data graphically from accessing it from the database. The main added value of the developed platform is extending the existing FIWARE platform to support ACDC hybrid device monitoring and modeling the data according to SARGON ontology. Instead of going through all the processes one by one, or having different platforms to do all of these one by one, the goal is to use and modify Entirety as one platform to make the process simpler. For our case, from getting various types of data from the sensors to different types of graphical visualization of the data, the goal

¹<https://git.rwth-aachen.de/acs/public/ontology/sargon/-/tree/master>

Figure 4: SARGON view in Web Protégé.

is to use Entirety to do it in a simpler way. Also keep in mind that where there is data, there we also need security, this is also something that Entirety provides us.

The developed sensing and monitoring infrastructure layer is illustrated in Fig. 5.

There are 9 components. This first step is to collect the sensor data through the MQTT Broker. The IoT Agent is connected with MQTT Broker and ORION Context Broker. The Entirety creates the entity of the device. Therefore, the data are saved in the MongoDB and the QuantumLeap subscribe the context broker and forwards the data to the CrateDB. Finally, the data are monitored in the Grafana. In the following, each component is described in detail.

FIWARE

FIWARE² is an open source platform that helps in the easy building and maintaining software applications and services. FIWARE comprises of components that make complex processes simple, cost-effective and secure, increasing the overall efficiency of the smart solutions (FIWARE, n.d.-a). The components include high-performance databases, advanced level Representational State Transfer (REST), Application Programming Interface (API). The platform components are integrated by standardized Next Generation Service Interface (FIWARE NGSI) which is the API exported by a FIWARE context Broker. The main FIWARE platform is used that provide optimum features in the field of majority of IoT-Applications. These include the Orion Context Broker, Quantum Leap and IoT agent. They are so-called Generical Enabler (GE). Those are the key component of our platform.

²<https://www.fiware.org/>

Figure 5: HYPERRIDE Sensing and Monitoring infrastructure Layer.

2.4 Component

Grafana: Grafana³ is a fully managed cloud based open source observability platform which allows the user to implement their applications and infrastructure. The property that makes Grafana a very good choice is that it consists of very promising open source observability software such as Prometheus, Loki and Tempo. Not only the features of the mentioned software are made into optimal usage but also it is free of any kind of expenses related to installation, maintenance and scaling. Grafana cloud specializes in the visualizing of high-level graph and insightful logs in a very short period of time in just a few simple steps. Generally doing so from scratch, that is creating an integrated observability stack from any other open source takes a lot of time that a user might not be able to afford. There are quite some features that Grafana Cloud provides. To begin with, Grafana provides full-stack metrics and logging facilities in a very short period of time. Furthermore, Grafana allows the user can bring their own data, this data can be processed by queries and later dashboards can be created with it. Most importantly, Grafana is fully managed, although the visualization, dashboards, data sources and etc would be running from the user's environment it will be managed in Grafana Cloud.

CrateDB: CrateDB⁴ is an open-source Structured Query Language (SQL) database. It is a combination of SQL concepts and features of NoSQL which includes scalability and flexibility. CrateDB gains popularity because of the simplicity and affordability when it comes to managing the size, speed and types of machine and log data. Therefore, leading customers to have very

³<https://grafana.com/>

⁴<https://crate.io/>

positive feedback. Because CrateBD is based on the concepts or syntax of SQL, users can get compatible with the system very easily. Users can process structured and unstructured data using SQL queries. Also, Different types of JOINS and aggregates can be used similarly to SQL and the performance in the speed remains the same. Therefore, all together scaling becomes very simple.

QuantumLeap: QuantumLeap is a REST service for storing, querying and retrieving NGSI v2 and NGSI-LD (experimental support) spatial-temporal data (FIWARE, n.d.-d). QuantumLeap converts NGSI semi-structured data into tabular format and stores it in a time-series database, associating each database record with a time index and, if present in the NGSI data, a location on Earth. REST clients can then retrieve NGSI entities by filtering entity sets through time ranges and spatial operators. Note that, from the client's standpoint, these queries are defined on NGSI entities as opposed to database tables. However, the query functionality available through the REST interface is quite basic and most complex queries typically require clients to use the database directly.

Entirety: ENTIRETY is an open-source web-based application that gives consistency to the devices in IoT platforms (Haghgoo, Sychev, Monti, & Fitzek, 2022). This is done by governing and provisioning in a simple and unified way. Currently, the main focus of ENTIRETY is the large-scale smart energy domain applications. However, other domain-specific devices can also be an extension of ENTIRETY. In order to overcome the IoT diversity challenges, the core of the ENTIRETY is a SARGON ontology which is the semantic data model designed for cross-cutting the domain-specific information in the smart energy system which is modular, extendable and reusable. Moreover, the approach of entirety is a template based making it easily runnable as a Docker image.

Orion Context Broker: The Orion Context Broker is an implementation of the Publish/Subscribe Context Broker GE, providing an NGSI interface. Using this interface, clients can do several operations (Fig. 6):

Key functionalities:

1. Context information updating (e.g. update humidity);
2. Notification on context information change/updates (e.g. change in humidity);
3. Context provider applications registration (e.g. provider for humidity sensor within a room).

MongoDB: MongoDB ⁵ is an open-source, cross-platform, and distributed document-based database designed for ease of application development and scaling (*What is MongoDB?*, n.d.). It is a NoSQL database developed by MongoDB Inc. MongoDB database is built to store a huge amount of data and also perform fast. MongoDB works on the concept of "NoSQL" database, which is completely opposite to SQL. Hence it is not a Relational Database Management System. Data in MongoDB is not stored or categorized in tables whereas it is stored as a collection JSON based document. So, no schemas, tables, rows or columns. But, similarly, in MongoDB, a collection can have multiple documents which are basically rows, in this case, each document has multiple "fields" which are basically columns in this case and documents in a single collection can be defined as having different fields in this case.

IoT Agent:

IoT Agent is one of the components of FIWARE. The purpose of IoT agent is to allow devices

⁵<https://www.mongodb.com/>

Figure 6: Orion Context Broker (FIWARE, n.d.-c).

to send their data to and be managed from context Broker via their own protocols (FIWARE, n.d.-b). It is essential for the IoT agents to be compatible with the security features of the FIWARE platform and then the device programmer should receive the other common services. In effect, this brings a standard interface to all IoT interactions at the context information management level. Each group of IoT devices is able to use its own proprietary protocols and disparate transport mechanisms under the hood whilst the associated IoT Agent offers a facade pattern to handle this complexity.

Keycloak: Keycloak ⁶ is basically a web-based GUI platform for managing the accessibility of a user by maintaining the secured authorization of the user. Also, Keycloak is an open-source platform currently licensed with Apache License 2.0.

Keycloak Features:

1. Single-Sign On: The authentication of a specific application can be done via Keycloak and this needs to be done only once. That means Keycloak takes care of the login forms, authentications and etc for the user's specific application and the user does not have to worry about it.
2. Identity Brokering and Social Login: Via the admin console, social networks login can be activated by just selecting the social network that the user wants to activate. Same goes for Identity provider.
3. User Federation: Built-in support to connect to existing LDAP or Active Directory servers is available. Own provider can be implemented as well, given that Keycloak user has their application users in other stores.
4. Admin Console: Admin console allows administrators to centrally manage all aspects of the Keycloak server like Different kinds of access and permissions.
5. Account Management Console: Just like normal account management, users can update profile info, change passwords and link profiles from additional providers if they have enabled social login or identity brokering.

⁶<https://www.keycloak.org/>

6. Authorization Services: Keycloak provides fine-grained authorization. This lets the user to manage permissions for all services from the Keycloak admin console and allows the user to be more specific about the policies.

MQTT Broker:

MQTT (Message Queuing Telemetry Transport) is an open source communication protocol. Generally, it runs over the TCP/IP stack. When it comes to bandwidth and system resources, MQTT is very much efficient. For this reason, MQTT is highly cost efficient and is very much popular in the field of IoT (Internet of Things) and also IIoT (Industrial Internet of Things). The main uses of MQTT include data collection and transmission to the server. Moreover, Publishing data from the sensor node to the user device directly. Also, the Configuration of IoT and IIoT devices remotely.

In the MQTT architecture, an MQTT broker is a central software entity that acts just like a real estate broker which first does background checks on the parties involved and then after making sure that the relevant rules are enforced, the broker initiates a transaction (catchpoint, n.d.). Generally, there are two types of brokers which include Managed Brokers and Self-Hosted Brokers

Docker: The whole project is compiled in Docker and the project is deployed from it.

Docker is a software platform for building, testing and deploying applications. Docker isolates applications in the form of containers. The container contains all the necessary dependencies (such as libraries, system tools, and codes) that the application needs in order to run properly. Therefore, by using Docker, the user can instantly deploy and scale their application into any environment being guaranteed that their application code will run in the same way as testing. Docker consists of several components that include the Docker file, the Docker image, the Docker run utility, the Docker Hub, the Docker Engine, the Docker Compose and the Docker Desktop.

3 Experiment in German Pilot

To test the sensing and monitoring layer, the platform is implemented on the German pilot (Work Package 7) side. The switch gear data is collected and monitored with the developed platform. The switchgear is a self-build type. The important components used are:

1. Main contactors: Schaltbau CT1230/08 + CT1130/08;
2. Current sensors: LEM LF 1010-S current transducer;
3. Voltage sensors: LEM DVM 3000 voltage transducer;
4. Controller: WAGO 750 Series Modbus Bus-coupler;
5. Signal conditioning: self-made.

The development is based on the following step:

1. The IoT agent for switch gear is created in Entirety based on the SARGON ontology. The process is shown as follows in Fig. 7.

Figure 7: Register Device in IoT Agent.

Once the IoT agent was created, one table is created in the CrateDB (Fig. 8).

2. The parameters of the table are defined in the data model in the code as NGSIv2, NGSI-LD, JSON formats. The Quantum Leaps part is to read the formats of NGSIv2, NGSI-LD, and JavaScript Object Notation (JSON). Also, the Orion Context Broker has a role here for the Format checking.
3. The input data of switch gear is Comma Separated Values (CSV) file. The CSV Files are illustrated in Fig. 9.
4. The next step is to send the data with the MQTT Broker via the IoT Agent. This is done by python code. The data goes and is stored in the CrateDB. The code is presented in Fig. 10.

Schema	
Name	Type
category	STRING
consistof	STRING
controlasset	STRING
controlsproperty	STRING
createdat	STRING
current1m	LONG
current1p	LONG
current2m	LONG
current2p	LONG
current3m	LONG
current3p	LONG
current4m	LONG
current4p	LONG

Figure 8: Table created in CreateDB.

Timestamp	data_voltageP	data_voltageM	data_current1P	data_current1M	data_current2P	data_current2M	data_current3P
Thu Jul 28 18:00:26 2022	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Thu Jul 28 18:00:27 2022	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Thu Jul 28 18:00:28 2022	0	0	2	2	4	4	2
Thu Jul 28 18:00:29 2022	0	0	2	2	4	3	2
Thu Jul 28 18:00:30 2022	0	0	2	2	4	3	2
Thu Jul 28 18:00:31 2022	0	0	2	3	4	2	2
Thu Jul 28 18:00:32 2022	0	0	2	3	4	2	2
Thu Jul 28 18:00:33 2022	0	0	2	3	4	2	2
Thu Jul 28 18:00:34 2022	0	0	2	3	4	2	2
Thu Jul 28 18:00:35 2022	0	0	2	3	4	2	2
Thu Jul 28 18:00:36 2022	0	0	2	3	4	2	2
Thu Jul 28 18:00:38 2022	0	0	2	3	4	2	2

Figure 9: Switch gear data.

5. The data is now uploaded in the CrateDB. The records are illustrated in Fig. 11 and 12.
6. We can portray this into grafana like this by the following Query example (see Fig. 13).
Then the data appears in Fig. 14.

```

import paho.mqtt.client as mqtt
import pandas as pd
import time

df = pd.read_excel('D:\switch_gear\Switchgear1.xls')
df["Timestamp"]=pd.to_datetime(df.Timestamp)
col_name=[]

for col in df.columns:
    col_name.append (col)
col_name = col_name[:-2]

for index, row in df.iterrows():
    client = mqtt.Client()
    client.username_pw_set("urn:ngsi-ld:boiler:boiler001", "secret")
    client.connect("137.226.248.224", 1883, 60)
    client.publish("/n5geh849992df6d1f7922/urn:ngsi-ld:Boiler:boiler001/attrs",
"dvP|{}|dvM|{}|dc1P|{}|dc1M|{}|dc2P|{}|dc2M|{}|dc3P|{}|dc3M|{}|dc4P|{}|dc4M|{}".f
ormat(
        int(row[col_name[1]]),
        int(row[col_name[2]]),
        int(row[col_name[3]]),
        int(row[col_name[4]]),
        int(row[col_name[5]]),
        int(row[col_name[6]]),
        int(row[col_name[7]]),
        int(row[col_name[8]]),
        int(row[col_name[9]]),
        int(row[col_name[10]]),
    ));
    client.disconnect();
    count= index+1
    print (count," row inserted in the table")
    time.sleep(3)
    if count == 10:
        break

```

Figure 10: Code for data publish to MQTT Broker.

timeinstant	voltage_m	voltage_p
1661960930000 (2022-08-31T15:48:50.000Z)	0	0
1661960933000 (2022-08-31T15:48:53.000Z)	0	0
1661960952000 (2022-08-31T15:49:12.000Z)	0	0
1661960955000 (2022-08-31T15:49:15.000Z)	0	0
1661960942000 (2022-08-31T15:49:02.000Z)	0	0
1661960949000 (2022-08-31T15:49:09.000Z)	0	0
1661960698000 (2022-08-31T15:44:58.000Z)	NULL	NULL
1661960927000 (2022-08-31T15:48:47.000Z)	0	0
1661960936000 (2022-08-31T15:48:56.000Z)	0	0
1661960939000 (2022-08-31T15:48:59.000Z)	0	0
1661960945000 (2022-08-31T15:49:05.000Z)	0	0

Figure 11: Data record in CreatDB part 1.

current1p	current2m	current2p	current3m
0	0	0	0
2	4	4	2
2	2	4	4
2	2	4	4
2	2	4	4
2	2	4	4
NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL
0	0	0	0
2	3	4	3
2	3	4	3
2	2	4	4

Figure 12: Data record in CreatDB part 2.

Figure 13: Grafana query setup.

Figure 14: Monitoring the switch gear data.

4 Conclusions

The deliverable provides a detailed description of various open source components, used in the development of the sensing and monitoring layer for the hybrid ACDC grid in the HYPERRIDE project. The sensing and monitoring layer is tested successfully in the German pilot.

This task (T5.2) is part of the Work Package 5 open source platform. In the next phase, the sensing and monitoring layer will integrate into the whole platform. The security part from task T5.3 will integrate with the sensing and monitoring layer. The service from Work Package 4 will build and test on top of the developed framework.

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